

Tosylation of Cellobiose and Thermal Analysis of the Product

A. RAMACHANDRA RAO, I. S. GUR and HARI L. BHATNAGAR*

Department of Chemistry, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra-192 119

Manuscript received 21 January 1984, revised 3 June 1985, accepted 30 August 1985

Cellobiose, a model compound of cellulose, has been reacted with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (tosyl chloride) in pyridine solvent. The products were identified by spectral studies and by determining the number of hydroxyl groups per cellobiose molecule substituted (*p*). The compounds have been subjected to DTA and isothermal TGA. The thermograms of the treated cellobiose samples show exotherms with peak temperatures between 478 and 483 K in nitrogen atmosphere. Kinetics of pyrolysis of the tosylated cellobiose samples have been studied by isothermal thermogravimetry in the temperature range 433-487 K. The range of decomposition temperature of the treated cellobiose samples is found to decrease with increase in number of hydroxyl groups substituted. The values of rate constant k_1 were obtained from the slopes of the plots of $[1 - (1 - \alpha)^{0.5}]$ vs time. The data have further been processed to obtain various thermodynamic parameters, such as energy of activation, entropy and free energy of activation, for the thermal degradation of the treated samples. With increase in *p*, the values of the energy of activation and entropy of activation are found to decrease, whereas the free energy of activation remains almost constant.

In continuation with our earlier work¹⁻⁴, reaction of cellobiose with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride and thermal degradation of the resultant products by isothermal thermogravimetry and their DTA behaviour have been investigated.

Experimental

Cellobiose (Koch-Light, England) was dried over P_2O_5 *in vacuo*. Pyridine (I.D.P.L.) was purified by refluxing it with solid potassium hydroxide for 6 h and then distilled, b.p. 115°. *p*-Toluenesulphonyl chloride (Riedel-De Haenag, Germany) was also dried *in vacuo* over P_2O_5 .

Tosylated cellobiose samples were prepared by treating pure cellobiose (2.282 g) with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (12.71 g) in dry pyridine (50 ml) at 308.16 K for different time periods. The reaction mixture was then diluted with cooled 95% acetone, stirred continuously in order to decompose unreacted *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride and then poured into cold water to get a precipitate of the tosylated cellobiose. The products were filtered out, washed thoroughly with water and then with benzene. The samples were dried in air and then *in vacuo* over P_2O_5 .

Infrared spectra (KBr) of pure cellobiose and of the products were recorded with the help of a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer. Nmr spectra ($CDCl_3$) were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer R-32, 90 MHz spectrophotometer.

DTA and TG studies: DTA thermograms of the samples were recorded in nitrogen atmosphere using Universal DTA-02 (VEB Laborelektronik

Halle, G.D.R.) at a heating rate of 12.5° min⁻¹. The detailed procedure for carrying out the DTA has been described elsewhere^{5,6}. TG studies were carried out isothermally at a pressure of 10⁻⁵ mm using a quartz spring balance¹⁻³.

Results and Discussion

Characterisation of products:

Ir spectra: The formation of *p*-tosylated cellobiose derivatives was well indicated by the presence of a sharp doublet at 1180 and 1190 cm⁻¹ and strong singlet at 1370 cm⁻¹ which are ascribed to symmetric and asymmetric stretch, respectively of the SO_2 group in C-SO₂-O-C linkage. A band at 550 cm⁻¹, which might be due to CH₂-O-S linkage, was also obtained.

Nmr spectra: The aliphatic region of the nmr spectra of the treated cellobiose samples was characterised by a signal appearing as singlet at δ 2.35 (ascribable to methyl groups of *p*-CH₃-C₆H₄-) in addition to other signals (multiplets) in the region δ 3.1 to 5.1 (due to rest of the protons of the cellobiose moiety). The resonances due to aromatic protons showed up as two doublets centred at δ 7.37 (*J* 9.0Hz, *ortho*-coupling) and 7.8 (*J* 9.0Hz, *ortho*-coupling) due respectively to protons *ortho* to CH₃ group and protons *ortho* to -SO₂- group of the tosyl moiety. From the integration of signals, it has been found that the product may be a mixture of molecules having different number of ester groupings which may have been formed by the esterification of even secondary alcoholic group. However, on the basis of analogy with

what is known about other systems⁷⁻¹⁴, it may be concluded that mainly the primary alcoholic groups of cellobiose molecule have been esterified.

Number of hydroxyl groups per cellobiose molecule :

The sulphur content of the tosylated cellobiose samples was estimated gravimetrically^{15,16}. The number of hydroxyl groups per cellobiose molecule substituted (p) of the samples, given in Table 1, have been calculated using equation¹⁷ (1).

$$p = \frac{342x}{3200 - 154x} \quad (1)$$

where, 342 is the molecular weight of cellobiose, 32 is the atomic weight of sulphur, 154 is the net increase in the molecular weight of cellobiose resulting from the introduction of one substituent, i.e. $-\text{SO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_3$, and x is the percentage of sulphur in the sample.

TABLE 1—NUMBER OF HYDROXYL GROUPS PER CELLOBIOSE MOLECULE SUBSTITUTED IN TOSYLATED CELLOBIOSE

Sample no.	Time of reaction h	Percentage of S(x)	No. of OH groups substituted (p)
1.	24	9.45	1.89
2.	48	10.25	2.16
3.	72	10.90	2.45
4.	96	11.45	2.67

Differential thermal studies :

DTA of the tosylated cellobiose samples was carried out in nitrogen atmosphere and the thermograms obtained are shown in Fig. 1. The thermogram of pure cellobiose⁴ exhibits two major regions of thermal activity. The first, an endotherm near 513 K, corresponds to the melting point of pure cellobiose. The second one indicates an endothermic decomposition at 573 K, followed by a small exotherm. The nature of the peaks, initiation, conclusion and peak temperatures of decomposition for cellobiose and the treated cellobiose samples with different numbers of hydroxyl groups substituted are given in Table 2.

The samples of tosylated cellobiose show exotherms with peak temperatures between 478 and

Fig. 1. DTA curves for treated cellobiose with p-toluene-sulphonyl chloride at 308.16 K : (a) 24, (b) 48, (c) 72 and, (d) 96 h.

483 K. The following observations could be made from the DTA thermograms of the treated cellobiose samples, (i) there is a lowering in the decomposition temperature of the treated cellobiose samples and (ii) the maximum of the exothermic peak is observed to decrease with increase in p.

Thermogravimetric studies :

Tosylated samples of cellobiose with different numbers of hydroxyl groups substituted were subjected to isothermal thermogravimetry. The plots of weight vs time at various temperatures for the thermal degradation of cellobiose tosylated at 308.16 K for 96 h (p=2.67) are presented in Fig. 2. The general shape of such plots of other tosylated cellobiose samples is similar. In some cases, where the reading could be taken immediately after introducing the sample, initially there was a small but rapid loss of the sample weight followed by a major weight loss. The rate

TABLE 2—MAXIMA IN DTA THERMOGRAMS FOR TOSYLATED CELLOBIOSE SAMPLES

Sl. no.	Samples	No. of OH groups substituted (p)	Nature of the peak	Peak temp. K	Initiation temp. K	Conclusion temp. K
1.	Cellobiose	—	Endo	518, 573		
2.	Cellobiose treated with tosyl chloride at 308.16 K for 24 h	1.89	Exo	483.16	428.16	528.16
3.	Cellobiose treated with tosyl chloride at 308.16 K for 48 h	2.16	Exo	488.16	428.16	518.16
4.	Cellobiose treated with tosyl chloride at 308.16 K for 72 h	2.45	Exo	478.16	438.16	528.16
5.	Cellobiose treated with tosyl chloride at 308.16 K for 96 h	2.67	Exo	478.16	438.16	538.16

Fig. 2. Plots of weight vs time for thermal degradation of cellobiose treated with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride at 308.16 K for 96 h : (○) 468.16, (△) 440.16, (□) 434.16, and (●) 459.16 K.

of major weight loss started decreasing after some time and ultimately the weight became constant. The initial small weight loss is attributed to the loss of sorbed moisture and has been neglected.

Evaluation of kinetic parameters :

The values of the degree of degradation, α , at various times of degradation were calculated using equation (2).

$$\alpha = (W_1 - W_t) / (W_1 - W_f) \quad (2)$$

where, W_1 , W_t and W_f represent the initial weight, weight at time 't' of degradation and the final weight of sample, respectively. The degree of degradation was calculated by considering the initial weight to be the weight at the point of inflection between the initial rapid weight loss and the final major weight loss, and the corresponding time was taken as the zero time.

The plots of the values of α vs reduced time $t/t_{0.5}$ showed significant scattering which suggested the non-applicability of Avrami-Erofeev equation to these systems. The data were observed to fit the curves derived from equation (3).

$$[1 - (1 - \alpha)^{0.5}] = (u/r)t = k_1 t \quad (3)$$

which describes¹⁸ rate of reaction controlled by the movement of an interface at constant velocity 'u' for a disc or a cylinder of radius 'r'. The values of rate constant (k_1) given by (u/r) , could be obtained from the slopes of the plots of $[1 - (1 - \alpha)^{0.5}]$ vs time 't'. Such plots for tosylated cellobiose sample with $p=2.67$ are shown in Fig. 3, and for the other samples also the plots were found to be of similar nature. The values of the energy of activation (ΔE) and the frequency factor (A) have been determined using Arrhenius equation and the plots of $\ln k_1$ vs T^{-1} for the four samples (Fig. 4) were found to be linear.

Fig. 3. Plots for thermal degradation of cellobiose treated with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride at 308.16 K for 96 h : (○) 468.16, (△) 440.16, (□) 434.16, and (●) 459.16 K.

Fig. 4. Plots of $\ln k_1$ vs $1/T$ for thermal degradation of cellobiose treated with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride at 308.16 K : (a) 24, (b) 48, (c) 72, and (d) 96 h.

TABLE 3—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS, CHAR YIELD AND TEMPERATURE RANGE FOR THERMAL DEGRADATION OF SAMPLES

Sample no.	Temp. range for thermal degradation K	ΔE kJ mol ⁻¹	A s ⁻¹	ΔS^* J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔG^* kJ mol ⁻¹	Average char yield %
1.	491.16-536.16	104.31		-110.57	154.42	
2.	433.16-463.16	75.54	90.85 × 10 ⁴	-134.18	135.00	20.86
3.	433.16-487.16	72.07	17.5 × 10 ⁴	-147.81	137.57	23.88
4.	443.16-485.16	59.18	73.88 × 10 ⁴	-174.14	136.35	24.80
5.	434.16-468.16	47.58	31.06 × 10 ⁴	-200.48	136.34	25.56

* Values calculated at 443.16 K.

Assuming the enthalpy of activation ΔH to be equal to the energy of activation ΔE , the entropy of activation ΔS^* , and the free-energy of activation ΔG^* , were determined using equations (4) and (5), respectively.

$$e^{\Delta S^*/R} = \Delta h/kT \quad (4)$$

and

$$\Delta G^* = \Delta H^* - T\Delta S^* \quad (5)$$

The values of ΔS^* and ΔG^* have been calculated at 443.16 K.

The temperature range of thermal degradation, the average percent of char yield and various thermodynamic parameters for the thermal degradation of the tosylated cellobiose samples are listed in Table 3.

It has been observed that the values of the energy of activation for the pyrolytic degradation of the tosylated cellobiose samples are less than that of pure cellobiose and have been found to decrease with the increase in the sulphur content or with the increase in the number of hydroxyl groups substituted by tosyl groups. With increase in sulphur content, the amount of char has been found to increase, indicating that smaller amounts of volatile products are formed in case of tosylated cellobiose samples. This suggests that the mechanism for the thermal degradation of these samples is different from that of cellobiose. This is supported by the fact that ΔG^* for the thermal degradation of cellobiose is different from that of tosylated cellobiose samples. Detosylation and dehydration reactions might take place simultaneously during the thermal decomposition of tosylated cellobiose samples. Dehydration reactions are initiated at much lower temperatures because these reactions in the tosylated cellobiose samples are catalysed by the sulphonic acid which is released by the decomposition of tosyl group. A probable mechanism for the loss of tosyl group may be as shown below.

The entropy of activation for the thermal degradation of the treated cellobiose samples is found to be negative in all the cases and becomes more negative with the increase in the number of hydroxyl groups substituted. This is because of decrease in the degree of freedom accompanying the formation of the activated complex with an increase of the number of hydroxyl groups substituted. The interesting point to note is that the free energy of activation is almost constant around 136.32 kJ mol⁻¹ in all the four cases. Thus, it can be concluded that the basic mechanism of the thermal degradation of all the tosylated cellobiose samples is the same.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to C. S. I. R., New Delhi, for research fellowship to one of them (A.R.R.). They are also thankful to Mrs. Parminder Kapoor for help in TG work.

References

1. O. KALA, I. S. GUR and H. L. BHATNAGAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 890.
2. O. KALA, I. S. GUR and H. L. BHATNAGAR, "Flame Retardant Action of Chlorine Compounds on Thermal Degradation of Cellulose", "Abstracts Annual Convention of Chemists", Indian Chemical Society, 1979, Phy-65, 28.
3. O. KALA, I. S. GUR and H. L. BHATNAGAR, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1980, **19**, 641.
4. S. BHATNAGAR, S. L. AGNISH and H. L. BHATNAGAR, *Indian J. Text. Res.*, 1981, **6**, 87.
5. J. C. GUPTA, S. BHATNAGAR, K. LAL and H. L. BHATNAGAR, *Indian J. Text. Res.*, 1979, **4**, 40.
6. J. C. GUPTA, S. BHATNAGAR, K. LAL and H. L. BHATNAGAR, *Indian J. Text. Res.*, 1979, **4**, 49.
7. K. HESS and N. LJUBITSCH, *Ann.*, 1933, **507**, 62.
8. A. L. BERNOULLI and H. S. STAUFFER, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1940, **23**, 627.
9. T. KRISER and R. SCHWEIZER, *Ann.*, 1935, **519**, 271.
10. J. COMPTON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1988, **60**, 395.
11. B. HELFERRICH and A. GNUCHTEL, *Ber. Dent. Chem. Ges.*, 1938, **71**, 712.
12. J. M. SUGIHARAM, "Advances in Carbohydrate Chemistry", Academic Press, New York, 1953, Vol. 8, pp. 1-44.
13. M. L. WOLFROM, J. C. SOWDEN and E. A. METCALF, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 1690.
14. J. W. H. GOLDHAM and J. K. RUTHERFORD, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **54**, 366.

RAO, GUR & BHATNAGAR : TOSYLATION OF CELLOBIOSÉ AND THERMAL ANALYSIS OF THE PRODUCT

15. F. G. MANN and B. O. SAUNDERS, "Practical Organic Chemistry", Longmans, London, 1960, p. 500.
16. H. T. CLARKE, "A Handbook of Organic Analysis, Qualitative and Quantitative", Orient-Longmans, New Delhi, 1978, p. 807.
17. "Cellulose and Cellulose Derivatives", eds. E. OTT, H. M. SPURLIN and M. W. GRAFFIN, Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1954, Part II, p. 1422.
18. J. H. SHARP, G. W. BRINDLEY and B. N. N. ACHAR, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, 1966, 49, 379.